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The ubiquitin-proteasome system is associated with regenerative capacity of the spinal cord and neurons.

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We studied spinal cord injury and regenerative response potential in the spine using a mammalian model of nerve injury associated with mutation of the Wallerian degeneration process and an axolotl salamander animal model of spinal cord regeneration. At one week post-injury, ubiquitin B and ubiquitin C were both among the genes most dramatically modulated. Uba5 or Uba6 were silenced following injury and in regeneration, as was Isg2012. Psme4 was a target of modulation following injury across setting. The ubiquitin-proteasome system is associated with regenerative capacity of the spinal cord and neurons.

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